

**Antibacterial Efficacy of Neem Tree (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) Extracts on
*Staphylococcus aureus***

Abubakari, S. I., Duwiejuah, A. B.* and Yahaya, D.

*Department of Biotechnology, Faculty of Biosciences, University for Development
Studies, Tamale, Ghana*

Correspondence author email: aduwiejuah@uds.edu.gh

Abstract

Multiple microbial resistance is a growing problem and the outlook for more effective antimicrobial drugs in the foreseeing future is still uncertain. This study determined the antibacterial efficacy of neem tree leaf and bark extracts on methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) as an alternative treatment method. An *in-vitro* study experiment was performed using neem extracts which were subjected to aqueous and methanol extraction of its active compounds. Powdered neem leaves and bark were soaked separately in different containers with water (aqueous) and methanol for three days before being filtered into containers and diluted to concentrations of 20%, 40%, 60%, 80% and 100%. Isolates of MRSA were cultured from swabs of door handles of selected buildings on the University for Development Studies, Nyankpala campus, on Muller-Hinton agar plates and subjected to a standardised disc susceptibility method. The different concentrations of neem extracts were tested on isolated MRSA incubated on nutrient agar using the Cork borer method. Results showed an increasing antimicrobial activity with increasing concentrations of both methanol extract of neem leaf and bark. Clearer zones of inhibitions were observed at a minimum concentration of 60%. There was no positive record of antimicrobial effect of aqueous extract of neem leaf and bark on cultured MRSA. Antibiotics were able to produce clearer and wider zones of inhibition compared to neem extracts. Methanol extract of neem leaves and bark exhibited in the *in-vitro* antimicrobial test of methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* was effective and yielded greatest zones of inhibition at 100% concentration and a minimum zone at concentration of 60%. Further studies should be explored for the best method for extracting the active ingredient before *in vivo* studies can be done.

Keywords: Antimicrobial, *Azadirachtin indica*, inhibition, methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, neem extracts

Introduction

The neem tree (*Azadirachta indica*) is an incredible plant that has been declared by the United Nations as the “Tree of the 21st century” (Gao et al., 2020). It is a sacred gift of nature and an omnipotent tree which is mainly found in the tropical region. The leaves of neem have been used widely to treat various ailments by humankind. It is economically feasible, effective for adsorption and also acts as a killer and disinfectant of some germs (United Nations Environment Programme, 2012).

Neem trees are natural herbs known for their insecticidal (azadirachtin, azadirachtin B, nimbin and salannin are active ingredients in neem that act by deterring insect feeding, disrupting their growth and development (Chaudhary *et al.*, 2017)), pesticidal, dental (nimbin, azadirachtin and nimbinin are used as active ingredients in toothpastes and toothpastes (Lakshmi *et al.*, 2015)) and therapeutic benefits (Damtew, 2022). Medicinal substances derived from different plants found in our environment have become the most researched sources of medicines (Salmerón-Manzano *et al.*, 2020). For this reason, traditional medicine development has been introduced into the university curricula to acquaint students with knowledge of medicinal plants and their secondary metabolites which serves as potential therapeutic agents (Kasilo *et al.*, 2019).

One of the main causes of skin and soft tissue infections is the gram-positive, round-shaped bacterium *Staphylococcus aureus* (usually found on the skin and in the upper respiratory tract) (Xiao *et al.*, 2022). According to Holm *et al.* (2022), 20% of healthy individuals are intermittent carriers and 60% are permanent carriers of *Staphylococcus aureus*. To prevent the spread of antibiotic-resistant bacteria before it is too late, it is urgently necessary to identify suitable alternatives to antibiotics for the treatment of bacterial infections (Diarra and Malouin, 2014). Therefore, it is essential to look into strategies that would decrease bacteria resistance and investigate different antimicrobial sources (Uchil *et al.*, 2014). New strains of microbes are emerging day after day as microbial infections are being treated. Multiple microbial resistance has been a growing problem and the lookout for antimicrobial drugs in the foreseeing future is still uncertain. Consequently, this study was to evaluate the antibacterial effectiveness of neem tree leaf and bark extracts against *Staphylococcus aureus*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

Swab samples were taken using sterile cotton swabs on the door handles of different location of buildings on the Nyankpala campus of the University for Development Studies (UDS). The locations included the Spanish Laboratory Complex, the Library (24/7 Reading room), the clinic, the lecture theatre, audio visual room and the offices of the central administration (Accountant office, Faculty of Agriculture Family and Consumer Sciences and Biotech office). These were collected, cultured for the detection of methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* from the door handles.

Fresh neem tree leaves and bark (Plate 1) were harvested from the field (University for Development Studies, Nyankpala Campus) into a clean zip lock bag to avoid contamination.

Plate 1: Powdered neem bark and leaf

Media and Reagents

All media prepared were done by following the manufacturer's instructions and protocol.

Bird Parker Agar Medium Preparation

Bird Parker media (Scharlau) was used to culture and isolate *S. aureus* from swabbed samples. 12.63 g of Bird Parker Agar Base powder was measured using an electronic weighing scale (ME-T analytical balance) and dissolved in 200 mL distilled water according

to the manufacturer's protocol. After cooling, the prepared suspension was autoclaved at 121 °C for 15 minutes to sterilise it. Rabbit Plasma Fibrinogen (RPF) was poured into 10 ml of pre-warmed water, mixed gently and added to the Bird Parker media. The media was then distributed into sterile petri dishes under a laminar flow hood and allowed to solidify.

Nutrient Agar Preparation

Nutrient agar (Oxoid, UK) was used to obtain pure isolates. Following instructions on the manufacturer's container, eight grams (8g) of nutritious agar was weighed using an electronic scale and dissolved in distilled water of volume 500 mL. Placed in a laminar flow hood was the mixture, which was autoclaved at 121 °C for 15 minutes before being allowed to cool and poured into sterile petri dishes.

Saline Solution Preparation

A prepared saline solution was used to pre-moisten cotton swabs before use and also for antibiotic test. 2.20 g of sodium chloride was measured using an electronic weighing scale and dissolved in 250 mL of water. After autoclaving the solution at 121 °C for 15 minutes, it was allowed to cool. The refrigerator was then used to store the solution.

Muller-Hinton agar

The preparation of Muller-Hinton agar for the antibiotic test. Using an analytical balance, 4.56 g of Muller-Hinton agar was measured and added to a conical flask along with 120 mL of water. The medium was carefully dissolved by careful swirling of the liquid. The mixture was then allowed to cool under a laminar flow hood before being sterilised for 20 minutes in an autoclave at 121 °C.

Neem Leaf and Bark Extracts Preparation

Two batches of neem leaf extract were made, one in distilled water and the other in methanol (Plate 2). Using a laboratory blender (Model 8000 Waring® blender), neem leaves were cleansed with fresh water, dry it in the shade for a week, and then ground into a fine powder. 50 grams of the powdered leaf were weighed, added to 500 mL of distilled water and 500 mL of methanol in a conical flask, and then left to soak for 72 hours whilst being occasionally stirred. After that, filter paper was used to separate the mixture into sterile containers (slow speed quantitative filter paper grade 203, LRG 18.0 cm - Q100). When ready for use, the sterilised containers were then stored at 4 °C.

Plate 2: Neem leaf extract

Diluting filtered neem leaf extract (stock solution: 100%) into concentrations: 20%, 40%, 60%, 80% and 100%. The formula $C_1V_1 = C_2V_2$ was used to determine how much distilled water was required to dilute the different percentages of concentrations from every 100 mL volume stock solution. This yielded the various concentrations. Where C_1 stands for the original extract concentration, V_1 for the initial extract volume, C_2 for the new or targeted concentration, and V_2 for the amount of water that must be added to reach the desired concentration during preparation.

Neem bark extract was prepared in two batches, one in distilled water and another in methanol (Plate 3). The process of making neem bark extract. The same process used to make neem leaf extract was used to prepare neem bark. It was cleaned with clean water, allowed to dry in the shade for a week, and then it was pulverised (broken into small pieces and then blended into powder using a laboratory blender: Model 8000 Waring® blender) to a fine powder. A conical flask was filled with around 50 grams of the powdered bark, 500 mL of either distilled water or methanol, and both mixtures were allowed to soak for 72 hours with intermittent mixing. The combination was then put into sterile containers after being filtered with filter paper (slow speed quantitative filter paper grade 203, LRG 18.0 cm - Q100). The sterile containers were then kept at 4 °C until they were utilised.

Plate 3: Neem bark extract

Experimental Design

Same method was applied to the treatments. Where different concentrations (0%, 20%, 40%, 60%, 80% and 100% each) of neem leaf and bark extracts were applied to each culture of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. The zone of inhibition on the cultured *Staphylococcus aureus* was the dependent variable, while the various levels of neem tree extracts concentration (0%, 20%, 40%, 60%, 80% and 100% each) were the independent factors. The study was limited to methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* samples swiped from the door handles of selected buildings on the Nyankpala campus of the University for Development Studies.

Growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* from Swabbed Samples on Bird Parker Agar

Swab samples taken from door handles were streaked on Bird Parker Agar media. Each petri dish was named in connection to the various swabs from the door handles for easy identification. All swabs were then streaked on their corresponding petri dishes containing Bird Parker agar and cultured for a period of 12 to 18 hours.

Culturing of *S. aureus* (Pure Culture) on Nutrient Agar for Antibiotic Test

Staphylococcus aureus colonies were removed from the Bird Parker media using a sterile loop (Fisherbrand™ Disposable Inoculating Loop) and streaked on nutrient agar for antibiotic testing. The entirety of the nutrient agar's surface was equally streaked.

Amoxicillin/clavulanic acid 2:2, ampicillin, cefoxitin, chloramphenicol, and ceftazidime were some of the antibiotic discs that were placed on the agar, covered, and inverted. The antibiotic discs and *Staphylococcus aureus* containing petri dishes were then incubated overnight.

Subculturing of Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA)

Confirmed MRSA from the antibiotic test were subcultured onto fresh nutrient agar by collecting colonies from the antibiotic test and streaking them evenly on the nutrient agar using sterile loops. The petri dishes were covered, inverted and incubated overnight.

Treatment of Cultured Methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*

Methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) were streaked on fresh nutrient agar and treated with drops of prepared neem leave and bark extract (different concentrations), and left in an incubator (Isotherm[®] Forced Convection Lab Incubator).

Incubation of Treatment

The treated subjects (petri dishes with the MRSA and neem tree and bark extract) were cultured in an Isotherm[®] Forced Convection Lab Incubator at 37 °C for the next 24 hours.

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration

The minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) of the neem leaf and bark extracts were determined using the agar well diffusion method. The lowest concentration of neem extract (1×10^8 CFU/mL) required to stop *S. aureus* from growing was called the MIC.

Data Collection and Analysis

Data was collected after 18 hours of incubation of applied neem extract treatment. Data collection was based on the zone of inhibition by each level of concentration of neem tree leaf extract and neem bark extract on the treated petri dishes.

The observation of antibacterial efficacy was carried out after treatment and data was recorded based on the zone of inhibition of methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* by the neem tree leaf and bark extracts. All the measurements were expressed at mean \pm SD. Data was recorded into excel and the mean mortalities of *S. aureus* for the two treatments (neem leaf and bark extracts) were compared and concluded that neem leaf extract had much effect on *S. aureus*. Additionally, the outcomes of the antibiotic tests were contrasted with a

reference list provided by the European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing. Breakpoint tables for interpretation of MICs and zone of diameters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Prevalence of *Staphylococcus aureus* from Door Handles

The experiment showed that out of a total of 12 (100%) samples, there were 8 (67%) prevalence of *Staphylococcus aureus* from door handles whilst 4 (33%) were negative (Table 1).

Table 1: Prevalence of *Staphylococcus aureus*

Sample code	Number of samples collected (%)	Positive <i>S. aureus</i> (%)	Negative <i>S. aureus</i> (%)
Biotech	1	1	0
LT 6	1	1	0
LT 4	1	0	1
R. R	1	1	0
FOAFCS	1	1	0
Acc	1	1	0
Food Sci	1	1	0
S. L	1	0	1
Micro Lb	1	0	1
AVR	1	1	0
CLN	1	0	1
CLN 2	1	1	0
Total	12 (100%)	8 (67%)	4 (33%)

Antibiotic Test on *Staphylococcus aureus*

All samples showed susceptibility to antibiotics except two which showed resistance to FOX and CAZ (Table 2). This means that the susceptible samples were either eliminated or could not grow around the antibiotics FOX and CAZ but could grow on other regions on the media, but the resistant samples were able to grow around FOX and CAZ. FOX and CAZ are antibiotics which were used to test the presence of MRSA. This proved that the two samples which showed resistance to FOX and CAZ are MRSA.

Table 2: Antibiotic test on *Staphylococcus aureus*

Antibiotics	Susceptible (%)	Intermediate	Resistant (%)
FOX	10	1	1
CAZ	11	0	1

AMP	12	0	0
C	12	0	0
AMC	12	0	0

Note: FOX = cefoxitin, CAZ = ceftazidime, AMP = ampicillin, C = chloramphenicol, AMC = amoxicillin/ clavulanic acid

Prevalence of MRSA

Out of the twelve (12) swab samples which were subjected to the antibiotic test, it was found that 4 (33%) were not *Staphylococcus aureus*, 6 (50%) were *Staphylococcus aureus*, and 2 (17%) were methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (Table 3).

Table 3: Prevalence of MRSA

Total Samples	Number of negative <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (%)	Number of positive <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (%)	Number of positive methicillin resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (%)
12 (100%)	33%	50%	17%

Figure 1: Prevalence of MRSA

Antimicrobial Test of Neem Extract on MRSA

The neem leaf extract made using aqueous showed no record of inhibition of the growth of MRSA on the media (Table 4). This means the MRSA was resistant to the extract of neem leaf extracted using aqueous, hence the MRSA was able to grow around the wells (6.00 mm) in which the neem extract was placed.

The neem bark extract made using aqueous also showed no record of inhibition of the growth of MRSA on the media (Table 4). MRSA was able to grow on areas around the wells in

which the neem bark extract was placed. Meaning there was resistance of the MRSA to the neem bark extract (aqueous).

Table 4: Antimicrobial test of neem leaf and bark extracts (aqueous) on MRSA

Concentrations (%) / Sample code	Neem leaf extract (aqueous)			Neem bark extract (aqueous)		
	Food S (mm)	AVR (mm)	CLN 2 (mm)	Food S (mm)	AVR (mm)	CLN 2 (mm)
0%	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00
20%	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00
40%	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00
60%	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00
80%	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00
100%	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00

The antimicrobial test of neem leaf and bark extract prepared using aqueous showed negative results for antimicrobial efficacy against methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). This meant neem leaf and bark extract prepared using aqueous was not able to prevent the growth of MRSA on the media, hence no zone of inhibition around the wells (6.00 mm) created on the media.

Antimicrobial Test of Neem Leaf and Bark Extracts (Methanol) on MRSA

Concentrations from 0% to 40% showed no level of inhibition of MRSA whilst concentrations above 60% showed zones of inhibition of MRSA on the media (**Figure 2**). The positive inhibition of the growth of MRSA on the media means the MRSA was susceptible to the neem leaf extract. Hence, could not grow on areas around the wells in which the neem leaf extract was placed.

Figure 2: Antimicrobial efficacy of methanol extract of neem leaf on MRSA

Also, concentrations from 0% to 40% showed no level of inhibition of MRSA whilst concentrations above 60% showed zones on inhibition of MRSA on the media (Figure 3). The neem bark extract made using methanol showed positive inhibition of the growth of MRSA on the media. This means there was no growth of MRSA on areas around the wells in which the neem bark extract was placed.

Figure 3: Antimicrobial effectiveness of neem bark methanol extract on MRSA

The antimicrobial test of neem leaf and bark extract using methanol showed positive results for antimicrobial efficacy against MRSA. This was proven by the susceptibility of MRSA to the neem leaf and bark extract prepared using methanol, which lead to no growth of MRSA around the wells containing the neem leaf and bark extract prepared using methanol. The positive results of antimicrobial efficacy were observed on concentrations above 40% of neem leaf and bark extract prepared using methanol. However, international studies showed larger zones of inhibitions (18 - 19 mm) (Maramba, 2015) and proved more effective with much lower concentrations. This interpretation may be due to known botanical fact that trees selected for the study from different locations may have exhibited different properties since they were found in different soils, varying climates and were under different chemical and biological flora (Maramba, 2015). However, the disparity in the different extraction methods wherein the active component of the leaf and bark were harvested into the solution (treatment) was better isolated using methanol in this study. Aqueous extraction of neem proved a negative result with respect to antimicrobial efficacy on MRSA.

Inhibition Effects of Neem Leaf and Bark Extracts

Neem leaf extract made with aqueous was not efficient against MRSA based on the findings of this investigation. This can be because the water used for extraction did not successfully release the neem leaf's active ingredients for the antibacterial test.

Neem leaf extract prepared using methanol was more effective (due to the clearer and wider zones of inhibition observed) compared to the aqueous extraction. This demonstrated that methanol was a superior solvent for extracting the neem leaf's active components for the antibacterial study. The antimicrobial test of neem leaf and bark extracts prepared using methanol showed that the treatment was more effective at 60% and 100% concentrations as also stated by Sarmiento *et al.* (2011).

The methanol-prepared neem bark extract produced findings that were comparable to those of the methanol-prepared neem leaf extract. Neem bark extract prepared with methanol was more efficient than neem bark extract prepared with aqueous. This demonstrated that the active chemicals in neem bark may be extracted more effectively using methanol for the antibacterial investigation. The leaves and bark extract of neem tree have been used widely to reduce *Staphylococcus aureus*. And will be economically feasible and effective disinfectant of some germs as this finding learn support from United Nations Environment Programme (2012).

Implication of the Inhibitory Effects of Neem Leaf and Bark Extracts

The extract's capacity to stop MRSA from growing on the media was demonstrated by the zone of inhibition. It also demonstrated that MRSA cannot flourish when neem leaves' active ingredient is present (Na'ala *et al.*, 2016). It was shown that the zone of inhibition increased with increasing neem leaf extract prepared using methanol concentration and decreased with decreasing neem leaf extract prepared using methanol concentration.

Neem bark extract prepared in methanol is more efficient than neem bark extract prepared in aqueous solution. This is to say there are some active compounds in neem bark that has antimicrobial potential, and methanol was a good solvent for extracting those compounds.

Conclusion

The antimicrobial effect shown on methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) by neem leaf and bark extract prepared using methanol was confirmed when no growth of MRSA was observed around areas on the media where the extract was found. This study proved that neem leaf and bark extract prepared using methanol exhibited *in-vitro* antimicrobial activity against MRSA started at 60% concentration. The study further showed that the antibacterial activity follows a dose-dependent pattern, of which the greatest zone of inhibition of MRSA growth by neem leaf and bark extract prepared using methanol was at 100% concentration.

Much potential is seen for the development of these drugs especially for the use against methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* but with ideal extraction methods. Antibiotics study done before the neem treatment produced greater and clearer zones of inhibition compared to the antimicrobial tests.

There was no effect of storage time on the neem extract on the methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. This was proven when the neem extracts were prepared in two batches, stored for two different periods and tested for their antimicrobial efficacy. The results showed no change in data recorded. The neem leaf extract made using methanol showed relatively greater zones of inhibition compared to that of the neem bark extract. This clearly suggests that the neem leaf extract made using methanol was more effective against MRSA compared to the neem bark extract. It is recommended that further studies should be explored for the best method of extracting the active compounds in neem leaf and bark before *in-vivo* studies can be done.

Acknowledgement

We acknowledged Mr. Abdul-Razak Alhassan at the Spanish Laboratory Complex of the University for Development Studies, Nyankpala campus for his support during the laboratory work.

Conflict of Interests

The authors of research article have no competing interest.

REFERENCES

- Uchil, R. R., Kohli, G. S., Katekhaye, V. M., and Swami, O. C. (2014). Strategies to Combat Antimicrobial Resistance. *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research: JCDR*, 8(7), ME01. <https://doi.org/10.7860/JCDR/2014/8925.4529>.

- Chaudhary, S, Kanwar, R. K., Sehgal, A., Cahill, D. M., Barrow, C. J., Sehgal, R., and Kanwar, J. R. (2017). Progress on *Azadirachta indica* Based Biopesticides in Replacing Synthetic Toxic Pesticides. *Frontiers in Plant Science*.8;8:610. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2017.00610. PMID: 28533783; PMCID: PMC5420583.s
- Damtew, M. (2022) A review on chemical compositions, medicinal value and other applications of *Azadirachta indica*. *AGBIR*,; 38(2); 268 - 272.
- Diarra, M. S. and Malouin, F. (2014). Antibiotics in Canadian poultry productions and anticipated alternatives. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 5(JUN). <https://doi.org/10.3389/FMICB.2014.00282>.
- Holm, M. K. A., Meiniche, H. K., Pedersen, M., Eriksen, H. B., Westh, H., Holzknecht, B. J., and Bartels, M. D. (2022). A randomized, placebo-controlled, double-blinded trial of MRSA throat carriage treatment, with either standard decolonization alone or in combination with oral clindamycin. *Trials*, 23(1), 1-8.
- Kasilo, O. M. J., Wambebe, C., Nikiema, J. B., & Nabyonga-Orem, J. (2019). Towards universal health coverage: advancing the development and use of traditional medicines in Africa. *BMJ global health*, 4(Suppl 9), e001517.
- Lakshmi T, Krishnan V, Rajendran R, and Madhusudhanan N.(2015) *Azadirachta indica*: A herbal panacea in dentistry - An update. *Pharmacogn Review*(17):41-4. doi: 10.4103/0973-7847.156337. PMID: 26009692; PMCID: PMC4441161.
- Maramba, C. (2015). An *in-vitro* study on the antibacterial effect of neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf extract on methicillin-sensitive and Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/285867827>.
- Na'ala, S. I., and Sufiyanu, S. (2022). Antimicrobial Activity of Neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss.) Aqueous and Methanolic Extracts against Pathogenic Bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*) and Fungi (*Candida albicans*). *International Journal of Science for Global Sustainability*, 8(1), 5-5.
- Salmerón-Manzano, E, Garrido-Cardenas, J. A.,and Manzano-Agugliaro, F. (2020) Worldwide Research Trends on Medicinal Plants. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*:17(10):3376. doi: 10.3390/ijerph17103376. PMID: 32408690; PMCID: PMC7277765.
- Sarmiento, W. C., Maramba, C. C., and Gonzales, M. L. M. (2011). An *in-vitro* study on the antibacterial effect of neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf extract on methicillin-sensitive and Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *PIDSP J*, 12(1), 40-45.

Xiao, P., Liu, J., Yang, X., Wang, Y., Chen, W., Wang, C., ... & Yan, G. (2022). Multi-site infection by methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in a six-year old girl: a case report. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 22(1), 210.

Gao, R., Hu, H., Fu, Q., Li, Z., Xing, Z., Ali, U., Zhu, J., and Liu, Y. (2020). Remediation of Pb, Cd, and Cu contaminated soil by co-pyrolysis biochar derived from rape straw and orthophosphate: Speciation transformation, risk evaluation and mechanism inquiry *Sci. Total Environ.*, 730:139119.

United Nations Environment Programme (2012). United Nations Environment Programme Neem: The UN's tree of the 21st Century. Nairobi: United Nations Environment Programme (2012). Available from: <http://www.unep.org/wed/tree-a-day/neem.asp>. [Accessed on 10 September, 2021]